

$$P =? NP$$

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Introduction

I would like to say right away: I have no education, only 9 years of school. But I ask you not to underestimate me.

I believe that every person on this planet has the right to speak and the right to think.

The idea expressed here is not a proof, but a refutation of the classical formulation of

$$P =? NP$$

I want to show that this question was posed incorrectly.

Definitions

I will show clearly, as is customary, why I am right and confident in my statement.

Let:

- **R** — solver (who exactly solves the problem)
- **t** — time (how much time they have)
- **g** — goal (why they are doing it)

Then the classical question becomes:

$$P_{R,t,g} = ? NP_{R,t,g}$$

Without these parameters, the question has no meaning.

Proof

In my proof, I want to show clear examples of how the formulation changes with the introduction of subjects.

Example 1: $P = NP$

Solver R_1 — modern computer

Time t_1 — 1 second

Goal g_1 — check if the number 97 is prime

Computer:

- solves easily (instantly)
- verifies easily (instantly)

→ Here $PR_{1,t_1,g_1} = NPR_{1,t_1,g_1}$

Example 2: $P \neq NP$

Solver R_2 — human without calculator

Time t_2 — 1 minute

Goal g_2 — compute the integral $\int x^2 dx$

Human:

- solves slowly (if at all)
- computer verifies quickly

→ Here $PR_{2,t_2,g_2} \neq NPR_{2,t_2,g_2}$

Example 3: $P \neq NP$ for one, $P = NP$ for another

Solver R_3 — schoolchild

Solver R_4 — calculator

Same task: 123×456

Schoolchild:

- solves slowly, verifies quickly $\rightarrow P \neq NP$

Calculator:

- solves quickly, verifies quickly $\rightarrow P = NP$

Conclusion

The classical question $P =? NP$
cannot have a single answer,
because it does not take into account **who is solving**.

I would also like to answer in advance a question that may arise while reviewing my material:

Why am I doing this?

I have always wanted to study our world and make incredible discoveries.

Someone can say the same:

"This is unacceptable from a mathematical point of view."

To that I reply: ask yourself —
who then will solve such problems? A computer?

Final words

Thank you for your time.

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